

Derivatization methodology in analytical separation

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Abstract : Derivatization is the transformation of one chemical compound into another with similar chemical structure. The chemical compounds specific functional group that involves in the derivatization reaction which transforms a educt to a derivate from boiling point, melting point, solubility, reactivity and chemical composition. This results in new chemical properties is used for separation and quantification. In HPLC there are two kinds of derivatization methods such as pre-column derivatization and post-column derivatization. The present study reveals that estimation of misoprostol present in misoprostol 100 mcg and diclofenac sodium 100 mg tablets by pre-column derivatization. The antidiabetic drug voglibose present in voglibose 0.2 mg and metformin hydrochloride 500 mg tablets has been estimated by using post-column derivatization. The pre-column derivatization has performed by adding 5% solution of methanolic potassium hydroxide into a flask containing blank, standard and sample solution separately. These solutions are chromatographed into HPLC. The post-column derivatization of voglibose by using taurine and sodium periodate reagents with fluorimetry detection. This method is specific, linear and accurate from 25% level to 150% level. The method is suitable for regular analysis.

Keywords : Pre-column derivatization, post-column derivatization, derivatization methodology, analytical separation.

Introduction^{1,4,7,8}

The study reveals that derivation method can be useful for the estimation of lower label claim drug products and lower UV absorbance drug substances. To determine the pre-column derivatization by HPLC for the estimation of misoprostol and diclofenac sodium present in misoprostol 100 mcg and diclofenac sodium 100 mg tablet has selected. The misoprostol has derivatisized by using 5% w/v methanolic potassium hydroxide at 40 °C and neutralized with 1 N hydrochloric acid. In this case the active has reacted with methanolic potassium hydroxide and gives rise to change in molecular structure with the attachment of 2 hydrogen atoms and 2 hydroxyl groups. Now the compound is giving more absorbance with good separation. But in the case of post-column derivatization the active substance has treated with reagent after passing through the column. To determine the post-column derivatization the voglibose 0.2 mg and metformin hydrochloride 500 mg has selected for the study. In this case the column effluent has treated with fluorescent reagents such as taurine and sodium periodate. The compound voglibose has induced by fluorimetric properties and it has been detected by fluorimetric detector. These two derivatization methods are useful for the quantification of drug substances present in dosage forms.

Structure of Misoprostol $C_{22}H_{38}O_5$
Molecular mass is 382.534 g/mol

Structure of Voglibose $C_{10}H_{21}NO_7$
Molecular mass is 267.276 g/mol

Results and discussion¹⁻⁴

The content estimation for Misoprostol and Voglibose are as follows.

- (i) Misoprostol : Assay : 97.7 mcg/Tablets
Percentage content : 97.0%
- (ii) Voglibose : Assay : 0.197 mg/Tablets
Percentage content : 98.5%.

Table 1. Final results obtained from six sets of sample preparation

Sl. no.	Misoprostol (mcg)	Misoprostol (%)	Voglibose (mg)	Voglibose (%)
1.	97.12	97.12	0.1970	98.50
2.	98.14	98.14	0.1980	99.00
3.	97.80	97.80	0.1960	98.00
4.	96.51	96.51	0.1950	97.50
5.	99.01	99.01	0.1980	99.00
6.	97.33	97.33	0.1990	99.50
Average	97.7	97.7	0.1972	98.6

The amount of drug present in both the formulation has estimated and the result obtained is well within the acceptance criteria. The assay content is 90% to 110% of active substance present in tablet dosage form. In this study we found that the drug added for making formulation is almost equal to which is recovered by derivatization procedures using HPLC. The amount recovered for misoprostol and voglibose is plotted in a linearity curve against recovery level from 25% to 150%. The percentage recovery estimated from both the formulation is well within the acceptance criterion of 98% to 102%.

Table 2. The recovery results obtained from 25% level to 150% level

Sl. no.	Recovery level (%)	Misoprostol added (mcg)	Misoprostol recovered (mcg)	Voglibose added (mg)	Voglibose recovered (mg)
1.	25	25.12	25.18	0.0520	0.0522
2.	50	50.26	50.36	0.1007	0.1010
3.	75	75.21	75.17	0.1504	0.1507
4.	100	100.08	100.15	0.1999	0.2002
5.	125	125.16	125.06	0.2503	0.2506
6.	150	150.14	150.06	0.3007	0.3011

Fig. 1. Voglibose standard chromatogram.

Fig. 2. Voglibose sample chromatogram.

Fig. 3. Misoprostol standard chromatogram.

Fig. 4. Misoprostol sample chromatogram.

Fig. 5. Linearity curve for Misoprostol recovery.

Fig. 6. Linearity curve for Voglibose recovery.

Experimental^{1,2,6}

Estimation of Misoprostol content by HPLC using derivatization procedure :

(i) *Chromatographic conditions :*

- HPLC system : Waters 2698 E separation module
- Chromatographic column : C8, 250 mm length and 4.6 mm diameter, 5 micron particle size (MOS C8 is used)
- Eluent A : Filtered and degassed mixture of 1.0% triethylamine in water and pH adjusted to 6.0 using orthophosphoric acid
- Eluent B : Methanol (100%)
- Eluent ratio : Mobile phase A : B (50 : 50)
- Pump flow : 1.5 mL/min
- Column oven : 25 °C
- Wavelength : 285 nm
- Volume of injector : 100 µL
- Run time : 45.0 min

(ii) *Method of analysis^{1,6} :*

(a) *Reference stock preparation :*

Transfer 100 mg of 1% misoprostol working standard in to a 100 mL volumetric flask, add 70 mL of water to disperse and sonicate for 15 min below 25 °C. The volume make up to mark with water. Finally the solution is centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 min.

(b) *Test stock preparation :*

Accurately weigh and transfer 5 tablets in to a 500 mL volumetric flask add 250 mL water to disperse the tablets, sonicate for 15 min at 25 °C. The volume make up to mark with water. Finally the solution is centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 min.

(iii) *Derivatization procedure^{2,4,6} :*

Transfer 10 mL each of blank, standard stock preparation and sample stock solution in to a separate 25 mL volumetric flasks. To each flask add 5 mL of 5% w/v methanolic potassium hydroxide shake well and allow to stand for 5 min at room temperature, then place the flasks

in hot air oven at 40 °C for 15 min with intermittent shaking. After 15 min remove the flask from hot air oven and allow cooling at room temperature for 40 min with intermittent shaking, then add 5 mL of 1 N hydrochloric acid to each flask and make up the volume with water. Finally the solution is filtered using 0.45 µ membrane filter.

(a) *Test procedure :*

Inject 20 µL each of blank, standard preparation and sample preparation into the chromatograph, record the chromatograms, and measure the peak response of major peak.

(b) *System suitability :*

System suitability is established by meeting the following acceptance criteria.

(i) Standard preparations RSD should be not more than 2.0%. (ii) Tailing factor should be not more than 2.0. (iii) Number of theoretical plates should be not less than 2000.

(c) *Calculation for active content :*

$$\frac{\text{ASP} \times \text{WSD} \times 10 \times 500 \times \text{PT} \times \text{AV} \times 1000}{\text{AST} \times 100 \times 100 \times \text{WSP} \times 100}$$

where ‘ASP’ is average area of test preparation; ‘AST’ is average area of reference preparation; ‘WSD’ is weight of working standard taken for standard preparation; ‘WSP’ is weight of sample for test preparation; ‘PT’ is percent purity of working standard and ‘AV’ is tablets average mass.

Estimation of Voglibose content by HPLC using derivatization procedure^{1,2,4,6,7} :

(i) *Chromatographic conditions :*

- HPLC system : Waters 2698 E separation module
- Chromatographic column: Amide, 250 mm length and 4.6 mm diameter, 3.5 micron particle size (X bridge amide is used)
- Eluent : Buffer : Acetonitrile (38 : 42)
- Sample cooler temperature : 10 °C
- Pump flow : 0.5 mL/min
- Column oven : 30 °C

Excitation wavelength : 350 nm
 Emission wavelength : 430 nm
 Injection volume : 20 μ L
 Reaction module temperature : 100 $^{\circ}$ C
 Run time : 30 min
 Flow rate of fluorescence reagent : 0.25 mL from pump 1 and 0.25 mL from pump 2

(ii) *Method of analysis*^{1,2,6} :

(a) *Reference standard solution preparation* :

Transfer 20 mg of Voglibose working standard in to a 200 mL volumetric flask, add 130 mL of diluent and sonicate for 15 min to dissolve the contents. The volume make to the mark with diluent. Further dilute 2 mL of the above solution to 100 mL with diluent. Finally the solution is filtered using 0.45 micron filter.

(b) *Test solution preparation* :

Transfer 5 tablets in to a 500 mL volumetric flask, add 250 mL diluent to disperse the tablets and sonicate for 15 min at 25 $^{\circ}$ C. The volume make to the mark with diluent. Finally the solution is filtered using 0.45 micron filter.

(ii) *Derivatization procedure*^{2,4,6} :

Prepare the fluorescence reagent by dissolving 6.25 g of taurine and 2.56 g of sodium periodate in to 1000 mL water. Filter the solution through 0.22 micron filter paper. The diluent is prepared by dissolving 1 mL trifluoroacetic acid to 100 mL with water. The column eluent containing standard and sample is treated with fluorescent reagent in a reaction chamber with heating coil temperature about 100 $^{\circ}$ C. The compound voglibose is reacted with fluorescent reagent inside the reaction chamber and it is detected by fluorescent detector.

(a) *Testing procedure* :

Inject 20 μ L each of blank, standard preparation and sample preparation into the chromatograph, record the chromatograms, and measure the peak response of major peak.

(b) *System suitability* :

System suitability is established by meeting the following acceptance criteria.

(i) Standard preparations RSD should be not more than 2.0%. (ii) Tailing factor should be not more than

2.0 (iii) Number of theoretical plates should be not less than 2000.

(c) *Calculation for active content* :

$$\frac{\text{ASP} \times \text{WSD} \times 2 \times 500 \times \text{PT} \times \text{AV} \times 1000}{\text{AST} \times 200 \times 100 \times \text{WSP} \times 100}$$

where 'ASP' is average area of test solution; 'AST' is average area of standard solution; 'WSD' is weight of working standard for standard preparation; 'WSP' is weight of sample for test solution; 'PT' is percent purity of working standard and 'AV' is tablets average mass.

Conclusion^{3,5,6}

The abortifacient and antidiabetic formulation drugs especially Misoprostol and Voglibose is very much difficult to estimate by normal HPLC separation methods. The derivatization method developed for both Misoprostol and Voglibose is specific, accurate and linear over the range from 25% to 150% level. The study is very much useful to evaluate the content estimation by separation of lower label claim and lower UV absorbance drug substances present in formulated drug products.

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